

The use of medication mobile application or printed medication tables in caregiving to elderly dementia patients with polypharmacy

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Introduction

Caregiving to elderly dementia patients with polytherapy, especially for family caregivers, can be quite challenging. Common problem in elderly dementia patients, especially if they live alone, is not taking their medications properly. It is very important for patients who suffer from chronic illnesses like congestive heart failure, arterial hypertension, diabetes, hypothyroidism, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and other, to take their medications regularly.

Family caregiving

Responsibility for managing medications for older adults and/or people living with dementia in the community often falls to informal caregivers. More information resources are required for this role, which requires specific medication management skills and knowledge and is further complicated by the cognitive decline of the care recipient. Informal caregivers are often expected to manage medications in a safe and effective manner for their older care recipient, who may also have cognitive impairment. Nurses, who may be in frequent contact with community-living older adults/people living with dementia, can be an important source of information, training and support for informal caregivers (1).

Sousa and coworkers discussed in their article about training program for a family caregiver. The prevailing length of a training program for a family caregiver of people with dementia is of six sessions over a six-week period, with one weekly session load, and an average duration of 100 minutes each. Methodologies most commonly used include discussion, problem-solving models as well as skills and strategies training. The themes discussed comprehend caring for the individual with dementia, information about the illness and the use of health and community resources. Regarding the assessment of the family caregiver, the most widely used instruments are demographic assessment questionnaires, self-efficiency and caregiver's burnout scales, as well as depression and quality of life measures (2). It is important to identify the factors of the burden on the caregivers of people with dementia living in the community to prevent early nursing home placement, deterioration of caregiver's health and reduce the adverse health outcomes for care recipients. A health-related policy should be formulated to help informal caregivers receive more professional assistance. Training opportunities should be provided for family caregivers to reduce the impact of caregiving on the delivery of effective care (3).

MEDICATION APPLICATIONS AND TABLES

While the most commonly used definition of polypharmacy is being on five or more medicines, definitions are variable, which can cause confusion for researchers as well as clinicians in practice. Numerical definitions of polypharmacy do not account for specific comorbidities present and make it difficult to assess safety and appropriateness of therapy in the clinical setting. There is a need for an internationally agreed definition of polypharmacy. The results indicate the need for a shift towards the term 'appropriate polypharmacy' using a holistic approach of assessing medication use in context of comorbidities present, according to best available evidence in order to optimize health outcomes (4).

I prefer the definition of **polypharmacy (polytherapy)** as the necessary and justified use of multiple medication (5 or more drugs), whilst **polypragmasia (polypragmasy)** would be the term for the inappropriate use of multiple drugs that includes one of these errors: too many medications, duplication of medications, dangerous drug/drug interactions or drug/disease interactions, and excessive duration of pharmacotherapy. Patients, especially elderly and chronically ill, visit more than one physician. Sometimes physicians do not pay attention on the drugs prescribed by other physician, and that is one of the reasons why dangerous drug/drug interactions or drug/disease interactions can occur.

Table of medications, including over-the-counter (OTC) drugs, designed as mobile application or printed version, with precise dose regimen, is something that every patient with

polypharmacy must have. Medication tables are especially important for elderly dementia patients and their caregivers.

Mobile application can be designed to have a feature of self-check (by patient or caregiver) when medication is taken in defined time with alarm ringing if the dose is omitted. The medication table must be up-to-date every time when the therapy is changed, which can be managed during the visit to general practitioner/family doctor.

It is also very important to record the possible side effects of the drug. Detailed information about the side effects, including hypersensitivity reactions are very useful to the physician when assessing the benefit-risk ratio for every drug. Side effects part of the mobile application for polytherapy could be designed to recognize the keywords in the description of the side effect and to alarm the patient or the caregiver if it is important to seek medical attention. Printed version of the table with detailed description of the side effect, provided by the family caregiver, would also be as useful, because elderly patients usually cannot give detailed information about the side-effects, and caregivers sometimes forget the details if they did not make a note immediately.

CONCLUSION

A role of family caregiver is a very demanding task, and maybe the most difficult part is managing medications of care recipient. Table of medications, including over-the-counter (OTC) drugs, designed as mobile application or printed version, with precise dose regimen, is something that every patient with polypharmacy must have. Medication tables are especially important for elderly dementia patients and their caregivers. Medications mobile application or printed medication tables could be a very useful tool for the caregiver and the patient, but could also be a reliable source of information for the physicians. Medical professionals play a very important role in helping family caregivers in their demanding task by providing them all necessary information about illnesses and medical therapy of the elderly dementia patient.

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